

ISic1274

I.Sicily inscription 1274

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication; building
(?)

Material

local stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140763

1. [—]K [— — — — — — —]

2. Δημήτηρ ἡ ἱερ [ὰ — —]

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492880

EDCS 39101643

PHI 140763

Bibliography

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